

A Metrological Hyperspectral Texture Similarity Measure using Kullback-Leibler Divergence

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Abstract A metrological hyperspectral texture descriptor, Relative Spectral Difference Occurrence Matrix (RSDOM) has been proposed in previous work. Due to the probabilistic nature of the feature, Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) is used for similarity measure. In the literature, several approaches exist to approximate KLD which is otherwise computationally expensive if processed directly for feature spaces of high dimensionality. In this work, we compare the performance of these approaches through a hyperspectral texture classification scheme. The result shows close performance of variational approach (using Gaussian mixture model) to direct processing (using binned histogram) with 600 % faster speed. **Key words**

Texture, non-uniformity, hyperspectral, metrology, Kullback-Leibler divergence.

1 Introduction

The notion of similarity measure is at the core of metrology. A proper choice enables quantification of all metrological properties such as bias, accuracy and uncertainty. It also reflects the true nature of the object being measured in contrast with empirical or ad hoc approaches. Accordingly, a feature is incomplete without an adapted similarity measure and vice versa. As such, both must be developed simultaneously to be in the spirit of metrology.

In this work, we intend to study similarity measurement for probability density functions (PDF). In image processing, many features can be expressed as PDF e.g. image histogram, co-occurrence matrix [1] and Gabor transform coefficients [2]. In the past, limited by computational power many resorted to metric reduction for reduced complexity and storage. For example, statistical moments such as mean and variance have been used to describe image histogram. Texture features such as energy, homogeneity and angular second moments have been used to describe cooccurrence matrix [1]. While Gabor transform produces features the same size as the input image, their quadratic sum over the image have been taken as the final feature [2]. Then, Euclidean distance or L2 norm is used for the similarity measurement [1,2].

While these approaches works in image retrieval or classification tasks, many image information are lost with no physical interpretation possible from the feature.

For metrological purposes, features in the form of PDF must be assessed accordingly without reduction to metrics. In this case, f-divergence measures such as Kullback-Leibler

divergence (KLD) [3] have been used extensively owing to its entropy properties. However, the direct application of KLD is laborious considering the need of histogram for feature representation. For multi-dimensional cases, the application of histogram is tricky due to the sparsity and computational complexity. As a result, various approximation [4,5] have been proposed in conjunction with the use of Gaussian mixture modeling (GMM) for feature representation.

Nevertheless, the performance of the KLD approximations and direct processing is not known. In this work, we address such lack via a texture classification scheme. In particular, we make use of a texture feature developed in previous work [6] and compare the performance of direct processing (using binned histogram) versus the approximations (using GMM). The rest of the article is divided as follows: in Section 2, a brief introduction to hyperspectral texture definition is presented. In Section 3, feature representation using binned histogram and GMM is outlined. In Section 4, similarity measure using KLD as well as different approximations are defined. In Section 5, a texture classification scheme is proposed and the result is analyzed. Finally in Section 6, concluding remarks for this work are presented.

2 Texture feature definition

The Julesz conjecture [7] states that textures with identical first- and secondorder statistics cannot be visually discriminated. Accordingly, we define texture as joint distribution of first- and second-order statistics [6], hereby denoted as α and β respectively. Consider a hyperspectral image I formed from a set $\mathcal{S} = \{S_1, \dots, S_i, \dots, S_N\}$ consisting of N spectra S . In this context of our definition, α refers to the probability of finding spectrum S_i , while β denotes the probability of spotting the spectral pair (S_i, S_j) as a function of spatial vector \vec{v} with distance l and orientation θ . As the direct representation in spectral space is practically infeasible due to the high dimensionality, we express α and β in spectral difference ΔS space:

$$\alpha^{(S_r)}(\Delta S_r) = \text{Prob} \left(d(S_i, S_r) = \Delta S_r \right), \forall S_i \in I, \quad (1)$$

$$\beta^{(l,\theta)}(\Delta S) = \text{Prob} \left(d(S_i, S_j) = \Delta S \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\forall i, j \in I, \|\vec{i_j}\| = l, \angle \vec{i_j} = \theta,$$

where S_r is a choice of reference sharing the same spectral range and resolution as \mathcal{S} while $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the spectral difference measure.

Due to metrological consideration, we use Kullback-Leibler pseudo-divergence (KLPD) [8] for calculating spectral difference. This is because KLPD is the only measure known to consider spectral ordering and therefore spectrum as a function. Its formulation allows natural decomposition of spectral difference, ΔS into shape ΔG and intensity differences

ΔW , an act impossible by L_2 norm such as root mean squared error (RMSE) and spectral angle mapper (SAM). Furthermore, the vectorial spectral treatment (RMSE, SAM etc.) also misses out on spectral permutation which otherwise provides high spectral discriminability. The metrological KLPD consider the spectral difference between two spectra S_1 and S_2 as:

$$d_{KLPD}(S_1, S_2) = \Delta G(S_1, S_2) + \Delta W(S_1, S_2), \quad (3)$$

where ΔG and ΔW are shape and intensity differences respectively, given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G(S_1, S_2) &= k_1 \cdot KLD(\bar{S}_1 \parallel \bar{S}_2) + k_2 \cdot KLD(\bar{S}_2 \parallel \bar{S}_1) \\ \Delta W(S_1, S_2) &= (k_1 - k_2) \log \left(\frac{k_1}{k_2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In expression 4, $KL(\bar{S}_1 \parallel \bar{S}_2)$ is the KLD on normalized spectra \bar{S} . The normalization constant, k is obtained by the integral of each spectrum (eq. 6):

$$\bar{S} = \left\{ \bar{s}_j(\lambda) = \frac{s_j(\lambda)}{k}, \forall \lambda \in [\lambda_{\min}, \lambda_{\max}] \right\} \quad (5)$$

$$k = \int_{\lambda_{\min}}^{\lambda_{\max}} s_j(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (6)$$

Encompassing both spectral and spatial distribution, the metrological texture feature T , of which we named RSDOM, is expressed as the joint PDF of α and β :

$$\begin{aligned} T^{(S_r, l, \theta)}(\Delta G_r, \Delta W_r, \Delta G, \Delta W) &= \\ \text{Prob} \left(d(S_i, S_r) = (\Delta G_r, \Delta W_r), d(S_i, S_j) = (\Delta G, \Delta W) \right) & \quad (7) \\ \forall i, j \in I, \|\vec{i}\vec{j}\| = l, \angle \vec{i}\vec{j} = \theta & \end{aligned}$$

An illustration of RSDOM is provided in Figure 1 considering the total spectral difference ΔS . For texture discrimination, the spectral shape and intensity differences are considered inducing a 4-dimensional feature space. On the choice of S_r , it has to be selected such that it lies *just* outside the convex hull of the spectral distribution for the entire set of texture. . For more information, we ask the readers to refer to [6].

3 Feature representation

Using Gaussian mixture model (GMM), RSDOM can be represented as a mixture of normal distributions. As GMM assumes an unbounded support, a diffeomorphism $\mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

Figure 1 – An illustration of RSDOM as joint distribution of first- (spectral distribution) and second-order statistics (spatial distribution).

is necessary as spectral differences are positive measures (eq. 8). A log-transform is selected for the diffeomorphism : $\tilde{\cdot} \stackrel{def}{=} \log(\cdot)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \tilde{T}^{(S_r, l, \theta)}(\tilde{\Delta G}_r, \tilde{\Delta W}_r, \tilde{\Delta G}, \tilde{\Delta W}) = \\
 & Prob\left(\tilde{d}(S_i, S_r) = (\tilde{\Delta G}_r, \tilde{\Delta W}_r), \tilde{d}(S_i, S_j) = (\tilde{\Delta G}, \tilde{\Delta W})\right) \\
 & \forall i, j \in I, \|\vec{i j}\| = l, \angle \vec{i j} = \theta
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

\tilde{T} could be modeled using binned histograms (BH). As RSDOM is a multi-variate PDF of $(\tilde{\Delta G}_r, \tilde{\Delta W}_r, \tilde{\Delta G}, \tilde{\Delta W})$, we modeled it using multi-dimensional histogram with L bins of varying bin sizes $\{b_{\tilde{\Delta G}_r}, b_{\tilde{\Delta W}_r}, b_{\tilde{\Delta G}}, b_{\tilde{\Delta W}}\}$ depending on the dimension. Alternatively using GMM, \tilde{T} can be represented using a set of K normal distributions $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$ with mean μ and covariance matrix Σ :

$$\tilde{T} = \sum_{i=1}^K \pi_i \mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \Sigma_i), \tag{9}$$

where π are the mixture weights.

4 Feature similarity measure

The Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) [3] is commonly used as similarity measure between two PDFs $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ (eq. 10). In this work, the similarity measure is taken involving KLD such that the symmetry is ensured (eq. 11). For binned histogram representation, the KLD is expressed in discrete form (eq. 12).

$$KLD(f\|g) = \int_x f(x) \cdot \log \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} dx \quad (10)$$

$$d(f, g) = KLD(f\|g) + KLD(g\|f) \quad (11)$$

$$KLD_{BH}(\bar{f}\|\bar{g}) = \sum_{j=1}^L \bar{f}(j) \log \frac{\bar{f}(j)}{\bar{g}(j)} \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{f} = \{P(1), \dots, P(L)\}$ is the normalized histogram with L bins such that $\sum \bar{f}(j) = 1$. If the histogram is multi-dimensional, it is to be collapsed into single dimension and evaluated in the same manner. To avoid division by zero, a small constant ϵ is usually added to the normalized histogram before KLD evaluation.

For the rest of the section, consider $f = \sum \pi_i \mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \Sigma_i)$ and $g = \sum \omega_j \mathcal{N}(\mu_j, \Sigma_j)$ to be GMMs. For GMM representation, there exists no analytical solution but several approximations for KLD [5], namely Gaussian approximation (eq. 13), nearest pair of Gaussians (eq. 14), product of Gaussian (eq. 15), matched bound approximation (eq. 16) and variational approximation (eq. 17):

$$KLD_{gauss}(f\|g) = KLD(\hat{f}\|\hat{g}), \quad (13)$$

$$KLD_{min}(f\|g) = \min_{i,j} KLD(f_i\|g_j), \quad (14)$$

$$KLD_{PoG}(f\|g) = \sum_{i=1}^K \pi_i \log \frac{\sum_{i'=1}^K \pi_{i'} z_{ii'}}{\sum_{j=1}^K \omega_j z_{ij}}, \quad (15)$$

$$KLD_{match}(f\|g) = \sum_{i=1}^K \pi_i \left(KLD(f_i\|g_{m(i)}) + \log \frac{\pi_i}{\omega_{m(i)}} \right), \quad (16)$$

$$KLD_{var}(f\|g) = \sum_{i=1}^K \pi_i \log \frac{\sum_{i'=1}^K \pi_{i'} e^{-KL(f_i\|f_{i'})}}{\sum_{j=1}^K \omega_j e^{-KL(f_i\|g_j)}}, \quad (17)$$

where \hat{f} and \hat{g} are Gaussians with mean $\hat{\mu}$ (eq. 18) and covariance $\hat{\Sigma}$ (eq. 19). Note that there exists a closed form solution [9] of KLD for Gaussians (eq. 20). On the other hand, z is a normalizing constant [9] considering D -dimensional feature space (eq. 21) while m [4] is a matching function (eq. 22).

$$\hat{\mu}_{\hat{f}} = \sum_{i=1}^K \pi_i \mu_i \hat{\Sigma} \hat{f} = \sum_{i=1}^K \phi_i \left(\Sigma_i + (\mu_i - \hat{\mu})(\mu_i - \hat{\mu})^T \right) \quad (18)$$

$$\hat{\Sigma} \hat{f} = \sum_{i=1}^K \phi_i \left(\Sigma_i + (\mu_i - \hat{\mu})(\mu_i - \hat{\mu})^T \right) \quad (19)$$

$$KLD(f_i \| g_j) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\log \frac{|\Sigma_j|}{|\Sigma_i|} + \text{tr}(\Sigma_j^{-1} \Sigma_i) - D + (\mu_j - \mu_i)^T \Sigma_j^{-1} (\mu_j - \mu_i) \right] \quad (20)$$

$$z_{ij} = (2\pi)^{-D/2} |\Sigma_i + \Sigma_j|^{-1/2} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mu_i - \mu_j)^T (\Sigma_i + \Sigma_j)^{-1} (\mu_i - \mu_j)} \quad (21)$$

$$m(i) = \arg \min_j KLD(f_i \| g_j) - \log \omega_j \quad (22)$$

5 Experiment and discussion

To compare the performance of direct KLD processing and its approximations, we apply a texture classification scheme on a hyperspectral texture dataset. For this, we utilize the 18 wood images from HyTexiLa [10] dataset as shown in Figure 2, each with 186 spectral bands. The wavelengths λ range from 405.37 nm to 995.83 nm at 3.19 nm interval, spanning both visible and near infrared region. The classification is based on nearest neighbor approach. Each image (class) is split into 25 patches and the ratio of training to testing is set to be 12:13. To avoid any bias, we repeat all classification using 100 trials with random selection of training and testing sets. The average accuracy along with their standard deviation are reported.

We select $l = 3$ and $\theta = 0$ in the calculation of RSDOM. For BH representation, due to computational power constraint we use $L = 40$ bins on all dimensions. For GMM representation, we select $K = 4$ for the number of GMM components based on Bayesian information criterion (BIC). We empirically select S_r (eq. 23) using $\text{erf}(\cdot)$ as the error function and $\tilde{\lambda} = (\lambda_{max} - \lambda_{min})/2$:

$$S_r(\lambda) = 1.5 + 1.5 \text{erf} \left(\frac{1}{200} (\lambda - \tilde{\lambda}) \right). \quad (23)$$

From the result in Table 1, three observations can be made. First, KLD_{var} is the best approximation for KLD with GMM representation. Second, the performance of KLD_{var} and KLD_{BH} is close. In average, KLD_{var} performs better than KLD_{BH} with the settings used. This shows that at this level, an indirect KLD calculation with GMM representation is adapted. With an extremely reduced computation complexity, the same or even better performance can be expected compared to direct KLD calculation. Third, it can be seen that the processing time for BH representation far exceeds that of GMM. In fact, BH is almost 600 times slower. Unfortunately, this large computational time does not reflect on its performance.

Figure 2 – 18 HyTexiLa wood images used in the texture classification.

To explain the lower score of KLD_{BH} compared to KLD_{var} , the heavy dependency of BH representation on L has to be considered. Due to computational limit, our selection of $L = 40$ might not be the most optimal one. Further examination is necessary to determine the optimal L value. Too little of L causes lack in representation accuracy, while too large of L induce data sparsity, rendering statistical significance irrelevant. The high dimensionality of RSDOM complicates the matter as sparsity is almost unpreventable even with moderate choice of L . Perhaps one solution is for L to vary depending on the dimension and not necessarily fix for all. Alternatively, chain rule for entropy measure (and therefore KLD) can be exploited by examining the independence between the dimensions.

On a side note, the classification result on the wood images cannot be indicative of RSDOM's performance. From its formulation in Section 2, one would have noticed

Table 1 – Texture classification result on HyTexiLa wood images along with their processing time per image. The texture feature, RSDOM is four-dimensional.

Similarity measure	Accuracy (%)	Processing time/image (min)
KLD_{BH}	89.66 ± 2.74	560.00
KLD_{gauss}	85.61 ± 2.81	0.94 (with GMM)
KLD_{min}	86.76 ± 2.66	0.94 (with GMM)
KDL_{PoG}	88.81 ± 3.43	0.94 (with GMM)
KLD_{match}	90.59 ± 2.98	0.94 (with GMM)
KLD_{var}	91.12 ± 3.08	0.94 (with GMM)

that RSDOM considers texture in a mono-directional fashion. Such approach is adapted for isotropic textures, but not so for directional ones as apparent in wood images. This is exemplified by the higher classification accuracy on food images (97.5 %) from the same dataset which are isotropic textures as reported in [6]. As reference, the overall classification accuracy on the entire dataset is reported to be 95.6 %, comparable to other state of the art (local binary pattern). Nevertheless, this motivates a multi-directional formulation in future to cater for directional textures.

6 Conclusion

We have studied and quantified the performance of both direct KLD calculation and its approximations. We did so by performing a hyperspectral texture classification on the wood images from HyTexiLa dataset. We conducted the texture analysis using Relative Spectral Difference Occurrence Matrix (RSDOM), a metrological, four-dimensional hyperspectral texture descriptor expressed as probability density function. It is shown that the KLD approximations with GMM representation is adapted. In fact, variational approximation demonstrates superior performance (91.1%) compared with direct KLD calculation with binned histograms (89.7%). This justifies the approach used in previous work whereby variational approximation is used as similarity measure for RSDOM with GMM modeling. The excellent performance of RSDOM has also been further confirmed via this investigation.

Although this work is expressed in the context of hyperspectral texture classification using RSDOM, the outcome is generic. The work shows efficiency of using GMM (decrease in computational time by 600%) for feature representation resembling a distribution. In conjunction with Kullback-Leibler divergence, the similarity measurement can be performed accurately (increase in accuracy by 1.4%).

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